

Fire Susceptibility Assessment in the Carpathians Using an Interpretable Framework

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Abstract

Climate change has heightened fire risks, not only in traditionally fire-prone regions but also in Central and Eastern Europe, including the Carpathian region, posing significant ecological and socio-economic threats. This study introduces a comprehensive dataset with twenty-seven variables and an interpretable machine learning framework to assess fire susceptibility across the seven countries of the Carpathians. We implemented a two-folded approach: first, refining our predictor set using various feature selection techniques, and second, applying SHAP (SHapley Additive exPlanations) to improve interpretability. The optimized machine learning models, developed using H2O, demonstrated high predictive accuracy, revealing that approximately one-third of the study area (98,511 km²) is at elevated fire risk. Additionally, seven major fire hotspots were identified, providing valuable insights for policymakers and local communities to enhance fire prevention and management efforts.

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Introduction

Rising global temperatures and decreasing precipitation have led to more frequent and intense wildfires worldwide, extending fire risk into temperate regions like the Carpathians. The mountainous area, home to extensive old-growth forests and crucial ecosystem services, faces severe consequences from fires, including biodiversity loss, economic disruptions, and health hazards. Fire occurrence is influenced by a combination of climatic, vegetation-related, topographic, and socio-economic factors, with human activities being the dominant ignition source in Europe.

Most previous studies have been localized, lacking a unified analysis across the entire Carpathian range. This research bridges that gap by assembling a standardized, publicly available dataset and applying advanced machine learning techniques to develop high-resolution fire susceptibility maps. The study emphasizes the role of vegetation and human influence on fire dynamics, aligning with global trends while offering a more detailed regional perspective.

Materials and Methods

The study covered 39 administrative regions across seven Carpathian countries: Czechia, Hungary, Poland, Romania, Serbia, Slovakia, and Ukraine. Fire data from

NASA FIRMS's MODIS active fire dataset (2010–2020) was used to compile a balanced dataset of 5,173 fire events and an equal number of non-fire control points. The dataset incorporated climatic (e.g., temperature, precipitation), vegetation (e.g., NDVI, forest coverage), topographic (e.g., elevation, slope, and aspect), and socio-economic (e.g., population density, cropland proximity) variables from various sources and domains.

To refine our predictor set, we applied three feature selection methods – Variance Inflation Factor (VIF), Recursive Feature Elimination (RFE), and Least Absolute Shrinkage and Selection Operator (Lasso) – and used their combinations to identify the most influential predictors. These refined predictor subsets were then used to train four machine learning models: Multiple Logistic Regression (MLR), Distributed Random Forest (DRF), Gradient Boosting Machine (GBM), and eXtreme Gradient Boosting (XGBoost). Model performance was evaluated using multiple metrics, with ROC AUC being a key measure of accuracy. XGBoost, trained with 19 selected predictors, emerged as the best-performing model, achieving an AUC of 0.941.

Data and Software Availability

The MODIS data and all other explanatory variables used in this study are publicly available online without any access restrictions or the need for special permissions. The datasets generated during and/or analyzed during the current study, along with all related R codes, will be made publicly available in the Harvard Dataverse repository upon publication.

Results and Discussion

The study identified seven key fire hotspots, primarily located in lower-elevation areas near human settlements. The most vulnerable regions included the Serbian Carpathians (Borski, Braničevski), the Southeastern Romanian Carpathians (Mehedinți, Dâmbovița, Buzău, Vrancea, Bacău), the Transylvanian Plateau (Mureș, Brașov, Sibiu), the Ukrainian Carpathians (Lviv, Chernivtsi, Ivano-Frankivsk), the Hungarian Carpathians (Borsod-Abaúj-Zemplén, Heves, Nógrád), the Slovakian Carpathians (Kosický), and the Polish Carpathians (Silesian, Subcarpathian).

The key factors contributing to fire susceptibility included cropland density, population density, proximity to settlements, vegetation indices (NDVI), and climatic variables such as temperature and precipitation trends. Cropland density emerged as the most influential variable globally, indicating that human-modified landscapes are

highly fire-prone. NDVI had a strong negative correlation with fire occurrence, suggesting that healthier vegetation reduces fire susceptibility. The SHAP analysis provided deeper insights, revealing that topographic factors had localized effects on fire probability, warranting further investigation.

These findings reinforce the importance of integrating machine learning with explainable AI (XAI) methods to enhance fire risk assessment. This study contributes significantly to the field by providing an interpretable, data-driven approach to fire susceptibility assessment, offering a replicable framework for use in other regions facing similar wildfire risks.

Conclusion

This research presents a comprehensive fire susceptibility assessment for the Carpathians, identifying high-risk areas and key influencing factors. The fire susceptibility maps developed in this study can serve as a valuable resource for policymakers, land managers, and local communities, enabling them to implement targeted fire prevention and mitigation strategies. Future research will focus on refining models with more detailed land-use and vegetation composition data, exploring the temporal dynamics of fire susceptibility and vegetation changes, and investigating the long-term impacts of climate change on fire risk in the region.

As the study undergoes the publication process, further refinement and validation may follow based on peer review feedback. Nonetheless, the findings provide a

strong foundation for improving fire management and preparedness in the Carpathians.

Figure 1. The main steps of our research process.